

Socioeconomic Status, Climate Change, and Mental Health: An Interdisciplinary Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Given the documented evidence that the relationship to one's physical environment is a determinant of mental health outcomes, it is important to examine how psychological researchers could apply clinical and research expertise to tackle social policy concerns. This paper provides an overview of how socioeconomic factors contribute to mental health disparities, particularly those related to climate change. Fundamental Cause Theory, which discusses the ability of socioeconomic status to influence health through a number of pathways, is used to explain climate-related disparities and examine risk factors that arise due to lower SES on mental well-being, such as increased exposure to environmental hazards. This work discusses the importance of one's ecology and community infrastructure, the impact of unequal access to natural spaces, and additional structural impediments of climate inequalities. After reviewing the literature and highlighting the link between SES and climate-related impacts, this paper suggests policy-focused solutions to achieve climate justice and improve mental health. Moreover, it emphasizes that while green infrastructure, which refers to practices that incorporate nature into communities, will help combat climate-related disparities, it's also important to acknowledge the need to avoid green gentrification, which entails the reproduction of systemic inequities and can alienate or displace certain community residents. Finally, this paper aims to inspire other scholars to create institutional change as a means of serving communities which have been disproportionately marginalized by the impact of socioeconomic inequality during the climate crisis.

Keywords: Socioeconomic psychological disparities; Climate policy

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INTRODUCTION

Background

The ongoing intersection of the political and the personal requires that psychological researchers actively apply their work to the tackling of social barriers to positive mental health. Psychologists can have a crucial role in influencing policies, especially since policies based on psychological data can affect social behavior (Ruggeri, 2017). With regard to one policy issue — climate change — this paper highlights facets of socioeconomic status and explains, due to its well-encompassing categorical nature, how one's ecological relationship, access to nature spaces, and physical landscape explain climate inequities. More specifically, it asserts that one's socioeconomic status can partly explain climate-related mental health disparities. This work deploys an interdisciplinary perspective to explain psychological inequities through examining and applying Fundamental Cause Theory, which argues that socioeconomic status can be "...associated with a wide variety of resources that can be marshaled to improve health in a diverse and changing environment" (Chang & Lauderdale, 2009). After reviewing the literature, this paper proposes policy-focused climate solutions to reduce socioeconomic climate disparities.

Research Question

Our research question is "Which mechanisms relevant to underlying, socioeconomic status-related causes of health inequity, may contribute to reducing mental health disparities related to climate change impacts?"

PERSPECTIVE

Climate Change and Socioeconomic Status

Overwhelming evidence indicates that climate change remains a threat to many ecosystems, particularly since "specific levels of warming" are tied to the extinction and destruction of certain species and because it has the ability to endanger the health of humans, including those persons who reside within coastal areas (Huggel et al., 2022). Thus, it is documented that besides its ability to endanger individuals' security, climate change also has the potential to harm several organisms and influence one's habitat. In this respect, due to the ways that climate change can impact societies, understanding how it can damage one's mental health and severely alter one's relationship to their environment becomes important to the achievement of social-wellbeing and equity relationships between communities. More importantly, it is imperative to study whether and how people of lower socioeconomic disposition are more vulnerable to worse mental health outcomes because of their increased likelihood to face negative impacts from climate change.

What is Socioeconomic Status (SES)?

While the intersection of one's social identities with the environment plays a role in the impact of climate change, one identity that is especially important to examine in the context of climate inequality is SES. SES includes several components, such as the following: "occupation, education, income, wealth, and residence neighborhood" (Shafiei et al., 2019). More particularly, SES includes objective and subjective measurements, such as individuals' ratings of their placement in the socioeconomic spectrum, and some research has indicated that subjective SES is more strongly associated with well-being compared to objective measurements (Navarro-Carrillo et al., 2020).

In addition to these two metrics, SES is a strong predictor of an individual's morbidity as well as their mortality due to its ability to encompass several variables linked to health outcomes, such as the

ability of income to reflect “spending power, housing, diet, and medical care” (Winkeby et al., 1992). For instance, “the size and reach of people's social networks” usually has a positive relationship with social status they have (Cao & Smith, 2020). Furthermore, individuals often experience better mental health outcomes overall if they have greater social support, and familial or friend support has been demonstrated to moderate adverse stress effects (Bekiros et al., 2022). Similarly, metrics such as occupation measure “prestige, responsibility, physical activity, and work exposures” (Winkeby et al., 1992). Education illuminates one’s skills for acquiring “positive social, psychological, and economic resources” (Winkeby et al., 1992). Hence, it can be seen that SES is a tool for not just measuring one's position to others, but it also includes several determinants that can influence health outcomes.

When it comes to establishing and utilizing a framework for SES within the context of climate-related mental health outcomes, it is critical to take one’s economic standing and residential status as a guiding tool for studying disparities in psychological well-being. Regarding the impact of SES on climate change, individuals with lower amounts of income are impacted more by the effects of climate change since developing nations might be unable to ensure proper access to resources such as food and water, thus inadequately adapting to alterations in climate at an institutional level (Balasubramanian, 2018). In addition, these socioeconomic disparities will be exacerbated, as indicated by the fact that “up to 90% of low-socioeconomic status individuals with mental health disorders are already not receiving treatment” across the world (Koder et al., 2023). Moreover, from a geographical perspective, persons residing in cities are more likely to experience higher temperatures, increased air pollution, and fewer opportunities to access green space as well as bodies of water due to climate effects, in turn possibly impacting the likelihood of suicide or other mental health problems (Zhang et al., 2021). Indigenous and rural areas may also suffer due to climate-related destruction. For instance, First Nations groups in Australia, which already face socioeconomic disadvantages, will be more prone to undergoing more “devastating experiences of the destruction of the natural environment” (Koder et al., 2023).

Furthermore, there is a link between SES and specific mental health disorders. Broadly speaking, having a lower SES is linked to having more recurrent psychological problems, such as chronic stress, because individuals with lower SES have limited resources to manage threats to their well-being and survival (Kim & Cho, 2020). In turn, events that occur due to one’s socioeconomic disposition before adulthood can result in long-term impacts, and differential exposure towards certain stressors can play a role in producing socioeconomic disparities (Reiss et al., 2019). Among marginalized communities, this issue is exacerbated by experiences of discrimination or social isolation (Macintyre et al., 2018). More importantly, those who are of low socioeconomic disposition may also have “a potentially low capacity to adapt” to climate-related health effects and may not be able to “cope, manage, and recover from new environmental hazards or climate stress” (Ingle & Mikulewicz, 2020). Thus, climate effects exacerbate an already extant relationship between lower SES and mental health.

SES & Fundamental Cause Theory

Because of these aforementioned structural roadblocks, a macroscopic approach towards examining the effect of socioeconomic disposition upon mental health is needed. A persistent question that often arises is how inequalities between social statuses continue to be maintained over time. One theoretical framework that elucidates the link between socioeconomic disparities and psychosocial outcomes is Fundamental Cause Theory, particularly due to its ability to clarify the pernicious ability of SES to be pervasive as a determinant of well-being. For instance, Fundamental Cause Theory asserts that SES is associated with several factors that can impact health outcomes, and despite the fact that this link can persist through intervening mechanisms, resources such as knowledge and prestige can be used to

shield one's health from risk factors (Phelan et al., 2010). In other words, even though SES is linked with multiple disease pathways that can affect the likelihood of the development of disease, the differential availability of supports, such as social ties and power, can limit the impact of risk factors (Phelan et al., 2010). This is especially important because disadvantages based upon differential power might illuminate barriers to interventions and other roadblocks that might prevent at-risk behaviors from being developed. Since these supports aren't equally available to all people, the means by which climate change exacerbates those differences must be examined.

More specifically, regarding the application of Fundamental Cause Theory to climate-related mental health disparities, the physical environment and ecology are mechanisms through which socioeconomic and psychosocial inequities can persist. For instance, hot weather could lead to a higher rate of heat-induced stress and illness, which can reduce labor productivity and lead to economic loss (Matsumoto, 2019). Climate-associated losses can also be experienced due to weather changes, as seen in the case of "ecological grief" that can occur in response to environmental alterations, such as ecosystem loss (Cunsolo & Ellis, 2018). Moreover, climate-related impacts have the potential to cause strong mental health responses, such as hopelessness or anxiety, due to the close relationships that some individuals may have with their natural surroundings (Cunsolo & Ellis, 2018).

In addition to one's economic productivity and ecological connection, there is also the need to discuss how inequality of access to natural spaces affects mental health. For instance, research has indicated that feeling psychologically connected to one's natural environment, such as "feeling part of nature or seeing beauty in natural things," has a positive association with positive well-being, although this link needs to be investigated further (White et al., 2021). However, even if individuals may express an interest in utilizing nature spaces, one paper on access to green space in the United Kingdom during COVID-19 lockdowns suggested that there may be an inadequate supply of these spaces in certain residential communities (Lee et al., 2023). This can have drastic implications, as one paper asserted that "those living in regions with the lowest number of parks and green areas had 16–27% greater odds for depression and suicidal indicators" (Nieuwenhuijsen, 2021). There are multiple pathways through which greenspace mediates mental health, such as being able to "absorb noise from the environment", thus improving residents' mental health and their sleep quality (Chen et al., 2021). More significantly, green space has a "buffering effect on stress", as residents "who lived in neighborhoods with more green space were less affected by stressful life events than those who lived in neighborhoods with less green space" (Chen et al., 2021).

Even though the presence of green spaces is especially important because people residing in urban communities with greater green spaces are more likely to have lower mental distress and anxiety, it is critical to understand that individual self-selection, which is defined as movement towards green spaces, might also influence mental health (Barton & Rogerson, 2017). Nonetheless, it has been demonstrated that greenspace can affect well-being, as a review of literature found that "low-SES groups showed greater health benefits if they lived in a greener neighborhood, relative to other populations" (Rigolon et al., 2021). In addition, properly constructed, outdoor green areas can also help mitigate crime, and natural spaces can offer opportunities for interpersonal engagement (Joshi, 2022). Ultimately, while having greenspace within one's surroundings is associated with "lower income-related health inequality" (Barton & Rogerson, 2017), the quality of the greenspace's amenities, along with its facilities, is also important (Hoffmann et al., 2017). For instance, in regards to specific greenspace qualities, "positive mental health was associated not only with parks with a nature focus but also with green spaces characterized by recreational and sporting activity" (Nieuwenhuijsen, 2021).

On the other side, fenceline communities, which usually include low-income minority individuals, are uniquely impacted by air pollution and experience compounded effects due to

environmentally hazardous situations, such as infrastructural failures (Fos et al., 2021). More significantly, socioeconomic vulnerability can be paired with the effect of ecological issues in the case of environmental displacement, especially because class disparities influence the ability of individuals to adapt to environmental impacts, sustain their lifestyles, or cope with climate events (Jayawardhan, 2017). In turn, it can be seen that socioeconomic inequities can exacerbate problems that originate ecologically.

While ecological contexts and environments play a role in psychosocial well-being, there are climate-aligned policies and several policy recommendations that can tackle the link between socioeconomic status and climate change. For instance, one intervention would be to diversify economic opportunities and strengthen physical infrastructure, thus improving adaptation and giving communities their own tools to fight stressors (Jayawardhan, 2017). Another method can be to encourage community-wide initiatives aimed at improving mental health among low-income people and enhance psychological service accessibility, particularly for coastal communities or rural areas that may be more susceptible to experiencing disasters (Liu et al., 2020).

More specifically, community-wide steps can include empowering communities locally with the resources and tools they need to tackle climate impacts, such as “adaptive planning initiatives” that can include the following as described by one paper: “advice on the best ways of engaging individuals, communities and organisations in developing well informed responses and strategies, along with up to date, accessible information on local climate change impacts, scenarios and tipping points, and mechanisms for sharing learning about the most effective local and regional level actions” (Fritze et al., 2008). This step is especially important for initiatives related to climate justice because there exists a “double inequality” caused by climate change, as “regions and populations that currently have the greatest increase in diseases attributable to temperature rise are those least responsible for the greenhouse gas emissions that are warming the planet” (Ingle & Mikulewicz, 2020). Hence, even though vulnerable communities may not contribute to climate change, they are impacted at a substantially greater level compared to more privileged groups.

Future Directions

The impact of SES can be found on mental health can be seen in numerous ways, and the effect of climate change enhances and reinforces how SES challenges one’s psychological state. However, there are multiple mechanisms that can help to improve people’s mental well-being as it relates to climate change: green infrastructure and public policy.

Green Infrastructure.

The use of green infrastructure is one critical method that can be deployed to improve climate-related well-being. Urban green infrastructure (UGI) consists of spaces (e.g., parks and urban squares) that are composed of elements from nature (Hanna & Comín, 2021). As asserted by a separate paper, when it comes to planning urban infrastructure, green infrastructure specifically “..brings attention to how diverse types of urban ecosystems and built infrastructures function in relation to one another to meet socially negotiated goals.” (Grabowski et al., 2022). In addition, it plays a crucial part in climate change adaptation, such as the ability to manage stormwaters and limit environmental pollution (Ying et al., 2021).

One review indicates some benefits that may arise from green infrastructure, stating, “People in urban neighborhoods that are characterized by lower-income and older-age populations were disproportionately healthy if their neighborhoods contained accessible, good-quality public green space” and that urban trees could lower stress and enhance mental health (Nieuwenhuijsen, 2021).

Tree-planting within an urban space or utilizing green roofs can also limit the impact of extreme weather (Lawrance et al., 2022). Likewise, it is important to take into account the attitudes of community members when brainstorming tree-planting and other similar programs since communities, as demonstrated in the city of Detroit, may be resistant to these techniques or not feel as included during the decision-making processes (Carmichael et al., 2019). On the other hand, the same paper did find that residents indicated “widespread support for green infrastructure solutions” even though they also expressed concerns regarding city management or access to the resources and knowledge to implement these policies, thus underscoring the need for effective communication and collaboration when contemplating the success of these initiatives (Carmichael et al., 2019).

Despite the ability of green infrastructure to neutralize the impact of climate issues, green gentrification must also be avoided in the process. For instance, there is the possibility that newer green infrastructure initiatives can play a part in displacing residents that “urban greening was often meant to benefit” (Anguelovski et al., 2022), thus reproducing inequities that green infrastructure intended to tackle. Furthermore, marginalized residents who have lived in the community for a long time might feel a lack of belonging within green spaces (Joshi, 2022; Jelks et al., 2021). Ultimately, even though green infrastructure can be used in a beneficial manner, gentrification can be witnessed when there is a change in the landscape of a community paired with psychological and physical displacement, “capital reinvestment,” “social upgrading of an area by high-income in-movers,” along with other components (Quinton et al., 2022). Hence, certain green actions could result in isolating individuals that might benefit the most from green infrastructure. Therefore, it is also important to examine other options along with creating new green spaces, such as allowing individuals to access current areas and improving awareness about green spaces (Uchiyamaa & Kohsakabc, 2022).

Public Policy.

In addition to green infrastructure, several policies can be deployed to strengthen the relationship with one’s environment and also enhance communities’ structures, facilities, and resources. These policies could include targeted approaches at particular populations, such as economic assistance in the form of subsidies or guaranteed income for farmers in order to reduce the prevalence of suicide among this group (Padhy et al., 2014). At a broader scale, these methods of mental health mitigation involve ensuring better insulated housing to protect against certain extreme weather conditions and reduce fuel poverty, as “safe and secure housing” can be critical in determining positive psychological health (Lawrance et al., 2022). Moreover, the alleviation of food insecurity through better agricultural techniques which prioritize ecosystem health and limit carbon emissions could enhance well-being too (Lawrance et al., 2022). Above all else, it is imperative to make certain that practitioners become more aware of eco-anxiety and other psychological problems associated with climate change (Ingle & Mikulewicz, 2020).

CONCLUSION

In light of the limited applied research and utilization of mental health-focused techniques to tackle climate inequities, this paper discusses the role of SES in understanding the role of climate change on mental health and one’s relation to their physical environment. Given its critical influence on psychosocial well-being, Fundamental Cause Theory is used to explain the risk factors that perpetuate climate inequality by underscoring the aspects of SES, such as the ecological impact of climate change, changes in labor productivity, and influence of nature spaces; these factors are also broadly tied to the presence of environmental injustice within lower-income communities. While actions centered around

the implementation of green infrastructure can be used to tackle these disparities, the growth of green gentrification is also a real concern when studying effective formulation and implementation. Regarding the implications for policy and practice at individual and community level, more grassroots initiatives paired alongside institutional changes can enhance extant infrastructure and protect historically excluded residents. Furthermore, clinicians ought to become more mindful of mental health conditions associated with ecological distress. In addition, future research ought to further examine how the greenspaces can be repurposed and can be combined with other green initiatives to empower communities that need climate change supports. Ideally, researchers will continue to use existing scholarship to create institutional change by focusing on the intertwined reality of socioeconomic inequality and the climate crisis.

DECLARATIONS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

None.

FUNDING

None.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

Not applicable.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Not applicable.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The Authors declare they have no competing interests.

PUBLICATION DATES

Received: 04 April 2023

Accepted: 05 September 2023

Published: 1 October 2023

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